

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHO-PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DRIVER CANDIDATES FOR PREDICTING SUCCESS IN DRIVER TRAINING

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Abstract: *As driver training evolves, the demand for effective and resource-efficient educational frameworks intensifies. Based on experts' opinion, this paper examines the significance of the psychophysical characteristics of driver candidates that contribute to training success, with the goal of enhancing predictive capacity and individualizing instruction. Grounded in research conducted within the Serbian Armed Forces, this paper presents findings from a project initiated by the University of Defence in Belgrade. Results underscore the relevance of attributes such as logical reasoning, concentration, visual perception, stress tolerance, and psychomotor coordination, while also revealing expert uncertainty in quantifying their relative weight. The findings support the development of adaptive training programs and more efficient resource planning. By anticipating individual training trajectories early in the process, this approach enhances both pedagogical quality and operational efficiency in military and civilian driver education.*

Keywords: *Psycho-Physical characteristics, Vienna Test System, driver candidates, driver training.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Parallel to the technological advancements in the automotive industry, the process of training individuals in the operation of motor vehicles has also undergone significant development. In its early stages—spanning the late 19th and early 20th centuries—driver education was largely informal, relying predominantly on the acquisition of practical skills through hands-on experience, typically facilitated by the vehicle owner or a close acquaintance possessing the requisite knowledge and expertise. However, with the increasing incidence of traffic accidents, the necessity for a more structured and formalized approach to driver training became evident. Consequently, the first theoretical and practical lessons were introduced, along with examinations as prerequisites for obtaining a driver's license. In contemporary practice, driver training is conducted within specialized institutions, commonly referred to as driving schools, although alternative models also exist

Models of driver education vary across countries; however, several general typologies can be distinguished:

- *The classical training model*, which comprises theoretical instruction, practical driving lessons, and a final examination, all conducted within licensed institutions or driving schools;
- *The competency-based model*, which is less formalized but emphasizes the acquisition and development of concrete driving skills and appropriate traffic behavior;
- *The graduated driver licensing model*, in which training is implemented in multiple stages over a period of several years. In this model, the driver's license—and with it, full driving privileges—is acquired progressively through stages such as learner's permits, provisional licenses, and, finally, full licence;
- *Modern training models*, which concentrate on the development of specialized driving competencies, such as eco-driving, safe or defensive driving, and driving under specific conditions. These models extensively incorporate contemporary technological tools, including simulators and other digital educational resources.

Regardless of the specific training model in question, a common characteristic across all is their high demand for resources.

In the Republic of Serbia, driver training is conducted within specialized, licensed institutions (driving schools), predominantly through practice on training grounds and in public traffic, with simulators being

employed only exceptionally. In addition to civilian driving schools, training is also carried out by the Serbian Armed Forces (SAF), within a unit dedicated to driver education, which boasts a decades-long tradition in this field. Given the institutionalized nature of the training process, its long-standing tradition, as well as the extensive capacities and technical infrastructure—particularly with regard to practical training delivered at the standardized and unique facility of the "Beranovac" autodrome—the SAF is recognized as a leader in this domain, not only nationally but also in a broader context. What further distinguishes the driver training conducted by the SAF's specialized unit from other driving schools and training centers is the intensive and complex psychological preparation of candidates, along with a strong emphasis on fostering a sense of responsibility and traffic culture among trainees.

In line with the foregoing, the driver training process requires substantial resources—material, human, temporal, and otherwise—while efforts to optimize their utilization remain ongoing. To this end, the University of Defence in Belgrade has initiated a scientific research project, one of whose subsidiary objectives is the development of a mathematical model capable of reliably predicting candidate success in training, based on psychophysical assessments conducted prior to instruction. This model aims not only to forecast training outcomes with a high degree of confidence but also to identify individual strengths and weaknesses, thereby enabling the customization of instruction by tailoring training components to the specific needs of each candidate.

This paper presents the results of a study examining the relevance of selected psychological and physical attributes of driver candidates for the multi-criteria evaluation of their potential to successfully complete training. The findings lay the groundwork for improved prediction of the resources required for training, particularly in the context of so-called additional training, which is provided to candidates who fail the driving test on their first attempt.

2. PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DRIVER CANDIDATES RELEVANT TO THE SUCCESSFUL COMPLETION OF DRIVING TRAINING

The success of candidates in driver training is contingent upon a wide array of internal and external factors. Among the internal factors, several categories of psychophysical characteristics can be identified that facilitate the successful completion of training and, subsequently, the efficient and safe operation of a motor vehicle. The most prominent among these are typically considered to be attributes related to psychological stability, concentration and attention, psychomotor coordination, sensory capabilities, cognitive abilities, motivation, and a sense of responsibility (see Porter, 2011).

For the purpose of predicting training success, psychophysical characteristics were selected that can be objectively measured using standardized tests within the framework of the Vienna Test System (VTS - a psychophysical testing platform developed by the Vienna-based company Schuhfried GmbH), which was developed, among other applications, specifically for the assessment of driver capabilities (Kubinger, 2007).

From the available tests within the VTS, a battery of tests was assembled and administered to driver candidates prior to the commencement of training. The battery comprised nine tests through which sixteen variables were measured (a more detailed description of the tests can be found in Schuhfried, 2013):

1. Logical Reasoning Test – designed to assess the candidates' cognitive abilities, administered in the form of a specially developed adaptive matrices test within the VTS;
2. Cognitron Test – aimed at evaluating candidates' attention and concentration;
3. Determination Test – used to assess reactive stress tolerance, attention, and reaction speed;
4. Peripheral Perception Test – measures the ability to receive and process peripheral visual information, specifically the candidate's visual field breadth and capacity for divided attention;
5. Reaction Time Test – evaluates various aspects of reactive behavior, namely, the average reaction time as an indicator of response speed to relevant stimuli, and the average motor time as a measure of movement speed during planned activity;
6. Adaptive Tachistoscopic Traffic Perception Test – assesses visual observation skills, situational awareness, visual orientation, and perceptual speed in driving scenarios;
7. Traffic Risk-Taking Test – measures the candidate's propensity to take risks in specific traffic situations;
8. Driving-Related Personality Inventory – evaluates personality traits based on self-assessment, including the individual's willingness to take risks, perceived social responsibility, self-control, and psychological stability;

9. Driving-Related Item Set – used to assess dimensions such as uncritical self-perception, aggressiveness in interpersonal interactions, and attitudes toward traffic norms, commonly referred to as “emotional driving”.

The success of candidates on the driving exam is a function of all the aforementioned variables, reflecting a multicriteria nature. For the design of a multicriteria model aimed at predicting candidate success on the exam, one of the essential steps involves determining the significance of each variable (i.e., the candidates’ psychophysical characteristics) within the model. This procedure was conducted as part of the research activities under the previously mentioned project of the University of Defence and was implemented through a combination of methods, including expert opinion elicitation, linear regression based on feedback data from the tested candidates’ exam performance, multicriteria optimization techniques, and the application of metaheuristic methods.

This paper presents the results obtained through expert opinion collection.

3. DETERMINING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHOPHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DRIVER CANDIDATES FOR PREDICTING TRAINING SUCCESS

In order to determine the significance (i.e., relative weights) of the psychophysical characteristics of driver candidates within a multicriteria model for predicting their training success, experts in the planning, organization, and implementation of training within the Serbian Armed Forces were surveyed using the fuzzy Delphi method.

The task assigned to the experts participating in the weighting process was to assess and linguistically express the impact of each variable from the selected VTS test battery on candidate success in passing the driving exam. Their assessments were provided using a customized fuzzy linguistic scale, represented by triangular fuzzy numbers $A_k = (a_k^l, a_k^m, a_k^u)$, where the parameters of a triangular fuzzy number

correspond to the lower or pessimistic value (a^l), the middle or most likely value (a^m), and the upper or optimistic value (a^u) (see Ghazinoory, Zadeh, Memariani, 2007). The index k denotes the k -th characteristic being evaluated for its significance (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Fuzzy Scale for Assessing the Significance of Psycho-physical Characteristics of Driver Candidates for Exam Success

The aggregated opinion of the expert group for each individual psychophysical characteristic of the candidate, expressed as a fuzzy number $A_{sr} = (a_{sr}^l, a_{sr}^m, a_{sr}^u)$, is obtained by combining the individual assessments of all N experts according to expression (1), representing the average value of the resulting set of fuzzy numbers (opinions) for the k -th characteristic

$$A_{sr} = (a_{sr}^l, a_{sr}^m, a_{sr}^u) = \left(\frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N a_i^l, \frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N a_i^m, \frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N a_i^u \right) \quad (1)$$

In this specific case, all experts were assigned equal importance (although this is not necessarily required), by allocating identical weighting coefficients w_i (where $\sum_1^n w_i = 1$, N – denotes the number of experts).

The final expert assessment of the significance of a given psychophysical characteristic was determined after conducting the required number of iterations within the expert survey process, in accordance with the Delphi method as described in Bojadzijeve and Bojadzijeve (2007) and Ljubojević (2016). To ensure the stability of expert opinions, a convergence condition was established: the sum of the weighting coefficients assigned to experts who revised their judgments in the final round of the survey (ΔW), compared to the previous round, must be less than w_{gr} (%) of the total sum of weighting coefficients (see Expression 2).

$$\Delta W = \sum_1^n w_j^* < w_{gr}, \text{ where } w_j^* = \begin{cases} w_j, O_{jp} \neq O_{jp-1} \\ 0, O_{jp} = O_{jp-1} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

w_{gr} (%) – stability threshold of expert opinions (expressed as a percentage), where O_{jp} denotes the assessment provided by the j -th expert in the p -th evaluation cycle.

The opinion of the expert group regarding the significance of that characteristic for the overall success of the candidate on the driving exam is represented by a triangular fuzzy number $A_{sr} = (a_{sr}^l, a_{sr}^m, a_{sr}^u)$, whose membership function takes the following form:

$$\mu_A(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq a^l \\ \frac{x - a^l}{a^m - a^l}, & a^l < x \leq a^m \\ \frac{a^u - x}{a^u - a^m}, & a^m < x < a^u \\ 0, & x \geq a^u \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

A total of 13 experts participated in the present survey, all of whom, in addition to possessing theoretical knowledge, have many years of experience in military driver training. At the end of 2024 and the beginning of 2025, these individuals provided their evaluations across three rounds of surveying, from which the aggregated (consensus) opinion of the expert group was derived.

To determine opinion stability, a convergence criterion was established: the sum of the weighting coefficients assigned to experts who altered their assessments in the final survey round had to be less than 0.20 ($\Delta W < 0.20$), which effectively implies that 80% of the surveyed experts did not revise their initial judgments.

The normalized values of the expert assessments concerning the significance of the observed characteristics of driver candidates for their success on the driving exam are presented in Figure 2 and Table 1.

Figure 2: Expert Evaluation of the Significance of the Observed Psychophysical Characteristics Expressed as Fuzzy Numbers

Table 1. Significance of Psychophysical Characteristics of Driver Candidates for Success on the Driving Exam

Psychophysical Characteristic of the Candidate	$A_{sr} = (a_{sr}^l, a_{sr}^m, a_{sr}^u)$	Centroid	Dispersion
Logical reasoning	(0.096, 0.118, 0.153)	0.122	0.057
Attention and concentration	(0.087, 0.094, 0.113)	0.098	0.026
Stress tolerance	(0.073, 0.075, 0.080)	0.076	0.007
Visual field breadth	(0.075, 0.077, 0.084)	0.079	0.009
Divided attention capacity	(0.068, 0.069, 0.070)	0.069	0.002
Reaction speed to stimuli	(0.025, 0.043, 0.050)	0.039	0.025
Motor movement speed	(0.075, 0.077, 0.084)	0.079	0.009
Traffic situation assessment	(0.077, 0.081, 0.091)	0.083	0.014
Mental stability	(0.051, 0.055, 0.057)	0.054	0.006
Responsibility	(0.043, 0.050, 0.053)	0.049	0.010
Self-control	(0.050, 0.055, 0.057)	0.054	0.007
Risk avoidance tendency – subjective assessment	(0.043, 0.050, 0.054)	0.049	0.011
Willingness to take risks	(0.021, 0.035, 0.041)	0.032	0.020
Uncritical self-perception	(0.025, 0.037, 0.043)	0.035	0.018
Aggressive interaction	(0.025, 0.037, 0.043)	0.035	0.018
Emotional driving (attitude toward norms)	(0.040, 0.046, 0.049)	0.045	0.009

Table 1 also presents a comparison of the obtained fuzzy values based on the centroid method (Wang et al., 2006) and the width, that is, the degree of uncertainty (Hajjari, 2011). Among the results displayed, it is evident that the selected group of experts attributes the greatest significance for success on the driving exam to the following candidate characteristics: logical reasoning ability, ability to sustain attention and concentration, capability for traffic situation assessment, visual field breadth, motor movement speed, and stress tolerance. According to the experts, these six psychophysical

characteristics collectively account for more than 50% of the overall influence on exam success (specifically, 53.7%).

At the same time, this group of characteristics is also associated with the greatest dispersion of expert opinions—that is, the highest degree of uncertainty and disagreement among experts regarding the precise evaluation of their importance. In other words, while the experts agree that these attributes are of paramount importance for training success, they differ to some extent in quantifying the exact weight of their contribution.

4. CONCLUSION

A wide range of factors influence the success of driver candidates during motor vehicle training. By identifying the candidates' psychophysical characteristics and abilities prior to the onset of training, it becomes possible to predict their likelihood of success with a satisfactory degree of reliability. To achieve this, a suitable multicriteria model is required, as well as an understanding of the relative importance of each selected characteristic within that model.

This paper presents the results of an expert assessment of the significance of sixteen psychophysical characteristics of driver candidates, all of which can be objectively measured using an appropriate battery of tests within the Vienna Test System. According to these findings, experts assign greater importance to attributes such as logical reasoning, attention and concentration, traffic situation assessment, visual field breadth, motor response speed, and stress tolerance, as opposed to candidates' willingness to take risks, uncritical self-perception, or aggressive interaction with other road users.

To arrive at a definitive conclusion regarding the influence and relative weight of these characteristics within a mathematical multicriteria model, further analysis using additional methods is necessary. Such a model would allow for the early identification—immediately upon completion of psychophysical testing—of candidates unlikely to pass the driving exam on their first attempt. This would, in turn, facilitate the prediction of the additional material, time, personnel, and other resources required to support supplementary training.

Simultaneously, test results could serve as the foundation for designing individualized training programs tailored to each candidate's specific weaknesses, thereby increasing their chances of success. In this way, both the quality of driver education and the efficiency of resource planning and utilization can be substantially improved.

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LITERATURE

- Bojadziev, G., Bojadziev, M. (2007). *Fuzzy Logic for Business, Finance and Management*, Word Scientific Publishing, New Jersey, USA
- Ghazinoory, S., Zadeh, E. A., Memariani, A. (2007). Fuzzy SWOT analysis, *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, 18, 99–108.
- Hajjaari, T. (2011). Ranking Fuzzy Numbers Based on Ambiguity Degrees, *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 5(1), 62-69.
- Kubinger, K. D. (2007). Psychological test calibration using the Rasch model: some critical remarks. *Psychology Science*, 49(1), 49-56. doi:10.4018/s15327574ijt0504_3
- Ljubojevic, S. (2016). *Model odlučivanja organa saobraćajne službe u zadacima strategijskog transporta*, Doctoral dissertation, University of Defence in Belgrade, Military Academy, Belgrade, Serbia.
- Porter, E. B. (2011). *Handbook of traffic psychology* (1st ed.), Academic Press, USA.
- Schuhfried, G. (2013). *Vienna test system: test manual*. Modling, Austria: Schuhfried GmbH.
- Wang, Y-M., Yang, J-B., Xu, D-L., Chin, K-S. (2006). On the centroids of fuzzy numbers, *Fuzzy sets and systems*, Vol. 157, Issue 7, 919-926. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fss.2005.11.006>